

Reliability and Failure Analysis of Porcelain High-Voltage Surge Arresters

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Abstract— TVA identified an increasing failure rate of 132-kV (106-kV Maximum Continuous Operating Voltage) porcelain arresters on the 161-kV system. A cross-organizational team was formed to determine the root cause of the 19 arrester failures and provide solutions. The team researched arrester failure modes and solicited input from arrester experts. A root cause diagram is discussed and multiple failure modes were ruled out. Multiple failed arrester units were dissected indicating moisture ingress as the root cause leading to the recent failures. Computer simulations contrasted faults through the Metal Oxide Varistor (MOV) block stack versus faults flowing through the air cavity surrounding the MOV stack. All 19 failures were recorded by digital fault recorders (DFR). The DFR waveforms were compared to the computer simulations showing that the arresters flashed over the internal air cavity. Based on the available physical evidence, moisture ingress is the likely root cause issue for the failures from 2002 to date.

paper we will call this problematic surge arrester make/model - Brand X. Due to the impact on reliability, TVA management formed a cross-organizational team (Arrester Failure Team) to determine the root cause of the arrester failures and provide solutions. The team reevaluated the existing philosophy of arrester protection for SF₆ high-voltage circuit breakers and evaluated the safety implications of porcelain arrester failures. The majority of team efforts were dedicated to determining the root cause of the failures. For recent failures the team looked for failure mode evidence by dissecting the faulted arrester. Unfortunately, many arrester parts from failures prior to 2009 were unavailable to the team. Fortunately DFR data was available showing the voltages and currents related to the 19 arrester failures and this provided clues to the failure mode. The majority of this paper focuses on the DFR analysis and the teams conclusions.

I. Introduction

The Tennessee Valley Authority (TVA) continues to deliver 99.999% transmission service reliability by focusing on solving re-occurring problems. Recently TVA identified an increasing failure rate of 132-kV (106-kV Maximum Continuous Operating Voltage (MCOV)) porcelain surge arresters on the 161-kV system. For the purposes of this

Figure 1. Number of TVA Brand-X porcelain arrester failures per year (2010TD value is arrester failures January to June 2010).

II. Arrester Failure Rates

Figure 1 shows the number of failures for Brand-X at TVA since 2002. The Brand-X manufacturer stated in 2008 that their failure rate for Brand-X is 0.03% (see Figure 2). The TVA Brand-X failure rate is 7 times higher (2006-2010 data) than the manufacturer's stated rate. TVA has seen a similar failure rate (4.5 year average) for another manufacturer's porcelain arrester units (TVA Brand Y).

Potential reasons for the higher failure rate considered were 1) Arrester component problems that did not allow the arrester to perform as intended; 2) Improper application and ratings; and 3) Manufacturing issues.

Source	Rate
Brand-X Stated History	0.03%
Brand -X TVA 2006-2009	0.22%
Brand-X TVA 2010-to June 1	0.60%
TVA Brand - Y Porcelain	0.17%

Figure 2. Failure rates of porcelain arresters.

III Porcelain Arrester Construction

Figure 3 shows the primary components of the Brand-X single-stack unit porcelain arrester. The bulk of the arrester is the porcelain housing which is a hollow cylinder with smooth inside surface. The outside of the porcelain housing has sheds designed to achieve the appropriate external dielectric capability. Centered on the inside of the cylinder is the MOV block stack. This stack consists of 22, 6-kV MOV blocks stacked on top of each other to get the 132-kV rating. Some spacers and spring-type supports also make up the MOV stack. The housing has top and bottom metal end caps with O-rings to seal the inside chamber from the environment. The pressure relief device is incorporated into the end caps. To increase the inside air breakdown insulation level, the manufacturer inserts dry air, with 2.5 % helium, into the housing before it is sealed. The end caps are clamped tightly to the porcelain housing to hold the O-rings and the MOV stack securely in place.

Figure 3. Materials Used to Make Brand X Arrester

IV TVA Arrester Application

The majority of TVA 132-kV arresters are installed to protect SF₆ power circuit breakers from voltage stress associated with lightning strikes. Figure 4 shows a one-line diagram with Brand-X arresters installed at transmission line terminations. Since TVA has automatic line reclosing, a faulted arrester will be subjected to multiple fault clearing attempts. Testing requirements [1] [2] for manufacturers do not simulate reclosing applications and so TVA's use of porcelain arresters in this application is untested. In two of the 19 failures, porcelain was sent over 50 feet from the arrester mounting point. Because of this potential safety issue, all new 132-kV arrester applications at TVA will install polymer type arresters instead of porcelain type arresters.

EMTP analysis and recommendations by [3] supported the TVA practice of applying arresters to protect SF₆ line circuit breakers. Also, based on TVA's effectively grounded system, the continuous and temporary overvoltage ratings of the arrester were confirmed to be adequate for the application.

V Root Cause Failure Mode Analysis

The arrester failure team researched arrester failure modes [4], [5], [6], [7] and hired an industry expert [8], [9] to assist with failure analysis. All faults were occurring within the arrester so the outside insulation breakdown was immediately

Figure 4. Typical one-line equivalent circuit of arresters applied to protect SF₆ line breaker. (The EMTP-RV equivalent arrester circuit contains three components in parallel, MOV stack equivalent, capacitance of arrester unit, and air gap of cavity surrounding MOV stack.)

Figure 5. Root cause failure diagram. (All possible failure modes were excluded except for moisture ingress due to improper sealing.)

ruled out. This left two possible modes for failure. The fault could be going thru the MOV stack or around the MOV stack in the cavity with breakdown of the dry air/helium gas environment due to partial discharge creating ozone. Figure 5 shows the two decision model paths in detail.

For recent failures TVA was able to test the MOV blocks which had no physical signs of fault path going thru the MOV blocks. The tests showed MOV conduction waveforms expected for new blocks. Therefore, the team ruled out a major design issue with the arrester MOV blocks. The team looked at the possibility of the internal stack of MOV blocks being shifted during transportation and installation. Spring tension was found to be over 700 psi and it was determined that handling to overcome this force was unlikely. The team also ruled out pollutants as the likely cause of air insulation breakdown. This left moisture condensation as the likely cause of the failures. Moisture ingress can weaken the dielectric strength of the insulation within the assembly initiating partial discharge, a localized electric discharge resulting from ionization in the insulation system creating ozone as a byproduct. The ozone eventually reduced the dry air/helium insulation quality and the unit flashed (faulted) inside the housing from the top to bottom caps.

Figure 6 shows several indications of the possibility of moisture ingress into the porcelain housing. First, the team found two units where the bottom end cap was missing the solder seal. Second, the team saw several o-ring alignment issues when sealing the top and bottom caps. Finally several units with copious amounts of yellow adhesive were found which may provide a gap for moisture ingress. The most telling evidence was found in two units with rusted metal pieces which could only occur due to moisture. The team concluded that the recent failures have been due to lack of proper sealing of the arrester from the outside environment.

Figure 6. Supporting evidence of moisture ingress.

VI Residual Current Signatures for 2002-2009 Failures

The team had the physical remains of the recent failures but limited physical remains for older failures. Fortunately, the team had fault waveform signatures for all 19 faults of Brand-X arresters.

The equivalent arrester circuit is shown in Figure 4 with a capacitor and arrester stack in parallel [10]. A component was added in parallel representing an arc-gap component to account for the simulation of cavity air/helium insulation breakdown. This allows for computer simulation with the Electromagnetic Transients Program (EMTP-RV). The circuit simulation model and program waveform simulations are

shown in Figure 7. In this fault, the digital fault recorder (DFR) is located at the station with the faulted arrester. Before the fault, the air-gap is essentially an open circuit and the high impedance of the capacitor and arrester block stack conduct low levels of current. Once the air-gap flashes, the capacitor and MOV stack are essentially by-passed and the fault current is primarily limited by the system impedance.

Figure 7. Measured phase voltages and residual currents (top charts) and EMTP-RV simulated chamber air gap breakdown (bottom charts).

For TVA transmission systems this is typically dominated by the system equivalent reactance with typical ratios of reactance to resistance of 5 (78 degrees lag) to 7 (82 degrees lag). The recorded DFR waveforms of residual current show an 82 degree phase shift from pre-fault to post-fault condition as well as a DC offset in the current. You will notice an instantaneous jump from low current levels (A) to major fault current levels (kA). The measured and simulated signatures both indicate this event to be a breakdown in the dry air/helium filled cavity and a flashover between arrester end caps.

Figure 8 shows the EMTP-RV model simulation for a 20 block MOV stack failure. This simple simulation reduces one MOV block every 3 cycles until at 1 second no MOV blocks are in the circuit. This model uses the same system impedance as shown in Figure 7. Note that there is not an abrupt shift in current, no dc current offset, no instantaneous jump in current, and a gradual change in voltage reduction. If the fault was in this manner (thru the MOV blocks) some of these characteristics would be seen. The arrester team has seen other arrester units fail with this pattern, but this is not the DFR residual current signature for any Brand-X unit failures.

VIII Conclusions

Cross-functional teams are effective at identifying root causes to reoccurring equipment failures. If these failures have been on-going for some time some of the forensic physical data may not be available for the team to study. DFR fault recordings provide valuable data helpful to see if the equipment failures are due to one or more than one issue. In this paper the arrester failure team used DFR data to prove that the arresters flashed over the internal air cavity and was not a failure of the MOV blocks. Based on the available physical evidence, moisture ingress is the likely root effect of Brand-X arrester failures and the most probable root cause is improper sealing of the arrester when the units were manufactured.

Safety is a major consideration when using porcelain arresters. The team determined that use of line side arresters where automatic line reclosing is utilized is an application that has not been tested by the arrester industry for safe failure clearing. Because of this TVA has switched from porcelain to polymer type arresters. Plans are in progress to convert the existing 132-kV porcelain units to polymer units over several years. Automatic reclosing of circuit breakers for AC transmission lines after fault interruption is a common practice in the industry [11]. The TVA team recommends that the IEEE/PES Surge Protective Devices Committee working group responsible for [1] and [2] develop testing requirements to account for this practice.

REFERENCES

- [1] IEEE C62.11-2005, Standard for Metal-Oxide Surge Arresters for AC Power Circuits (>1 kV).
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Figure 8. The Brand-X unit was modeled with 20 MOV blocks in series making up the entire arrester conduction performance. The EMTP-RV model for the 9/19/2006 fault circuit reduced the stack one block at a time until at 1 second no blocks were in the model.

VII DFR Data Summary

Figure 9 shows the tabulated results for the 19 failures of Brand-X arrester. All show the phase shift, DC offset and instantaneous current increase expected when the dry air/helium gap around the MOV block stack breaks down. DFR sites have high current transformer (CT) multipliers set up to accurately capture high (kA) fault levels versus low amp levels. The pre-fault residual currents range from 1 to 114-A. The team attributed these values to be due to CT imbalance and amplified noise from the high multipliers. Based on this summary, the arrester failure team concluded all arresters failed in the same manner and the most likely cause was due to moisture ingress leading to air-gap breakdown.

#	Pre-fault T= - 1 Cycle		Post-fault +1 Cycle Starting at T=Fault	
	Ires_rms Fund-A	Ires_rms Fund-A	V to Ires Ph. Shift	DC Offset -A
1	2	1608	76	213
2	64	4243	79	1148
3	7	1610	82	813
4	6	1584	82	708
5	15	1604	82	638
6	4	980	82	235
7	6	939	79	573
8	4	2114	82	681
9	7	606	79	204
10	1	2250	79	896
11	1	4387	83	2075
12	7	6252	82	2720
13	11	4997	82	2275
14	2	3995	86	718
15	2	1321	75	432
16	13	10915	75	4557
17	114	12065	N/A	4442
18	101	8951	82	1421
19	8	5690	82	2022

Figure 9. This table shows the DFR pre-fault and post fault electrical data for the 19 arrester failures. Note that all units went from low residual current levels to high residual current fault levels in 1 cycle.